

Jan Jacobs graduated in 1973 as sixth industrial designer at the Delft University of Technology.

Until 1986 he worked as a designer of, mainly, office furniture in industry. Since '86 he is full-time professor in Delft.

His responsibility is the chair of Aesthetics in relation to product design. At the moment he is director of education and vice-dean of the School of Industrial Design Engineering. Within the field of industrial design in the Netherlands he was, a.o. chairman of the Association of Industrial Designers and chairman of nearly every design prize that existed the last decades.

Many of the products he designed where awarded as "good-design"

The first reaction from a designer on the field of tension between products and emotion will, as a matter of course be the idea of design, and then mainly concentrated on that which we with a very ugly word call "formgiving".

Of course, one can say, because "formgiving" is that aspect that is one of the specialties of a designer. But the real designer should know better. Because he must have experienced that other aspects, as well, will evoke emotions.

From my experience the following.

I worked for a manufacturer of office furniture. We, as designers within that design department, found that there existed a very interesting sheet metal, covered with plastic. We thought that we could use this material very well as a table-top for our desks. The main problem was however that we could not weld the profiles we needed for strength under the sheet metal, because that would leave marks on the plastic cover. So we came in contact with Loctite, one of the worlds leaders in glue-applications. Loctite developed a glue that would suit our production possibilities and a first set of table-tops was produced. We placed this set, as a test, in our own office and after a week there where some minor complaints. The test-users didn't like the new tops, they didn't feel right. We found that the glue had a vague, bad aroma, and this was the reason for the emotion of disgust from the users. A negative emotion, very direct and absolutely not mixed, as we learned most emotions are.

A second example is related to sound.

The drawers of our mobile cabinets made a noise that, our potential customers related to as a lack of quality. This noise only occurred with empty drawers, so in showrooms and on fairs we filled up the drawers with huge amounts of paper to avoid this pre-sale, negative, emotion.

By the way: in the September-October edition of the German magazine Form, there is an interesting article from someone, who announces himself as a sound designer. He states: "when designers let chance define the acoustical properties of a product, they risk the situation that the sound of a certain product will be in contradiction to the visual intention of the product". And of course we know that in certain segments of industry, for example in the automotive industry, designers and engineers pay much attention

to the sound of the exhaust system or the slamming of the door. Recently some of our researchers had a pilot project in this specific area, and I think that a further survey could certainly be of great value to the field of our externally paid research.

Emotion, and I absolutely believe that designers are aware of it, not only has a relation to the form, but has a relation to a whole set of properties. How does the product smell, how does the product sound, and when all these aspects do not match the product will evoke negative emotions to the customer and to the user.

When one takes a look at the literature that describes the history of product design, the history of products and the history of marketing, you will find that there is a clear pattern of describing product qualities.

For decades we have known that a product not only fulfils its primary tasks, such as "does it work", or "does it support a certain job", but a product also fulfils, as we teach our students, secondary tasks. The difference between those two is described in a thousand ways, but all of them deal with the same starting point that states that a product was and is more than just a materialistic help.

It seems obvious that only the aspects that deal with this secondary performance of a product have a relation to emotions, but, as I will explain, I am not absolutely sure about it yet.

When a designer, and I suggest that for the ease of the discussion we now only relate emotion to form, has a look on the product-emotion-relation, he can do it at three levels.

Arguing from the inside of the product to the outside we are first confronted with the emotions that a product spontaneously evokes, and where the designer is not especially aware of the possibility to manipulate these emotions.

The second layer deals with the emotions that the designer purposefully can develop by manipulating the form. And the third layer deals with all those aspects that we build around a product, mainly in the field of publicity and promotion.

But this is not all.

The designer is aware of the fact that all the emotions, from the

different layers, are influenced by the status of the relation between product and user. We can, for example, distinguish between an intended purchase, the purchase itself, and the use of the product, the possession of the product or the past-use situation. And to make it even more complicated, this whole structure is influenced by the kind of user and the time: Time that leaves its marks on culture, fashion and trends. So the whole area of products and emotions is much more complicated than we would believe at first sight. **11**

Let me show you some examples out of my own design practice to illustrate this complexity. As I stated before, I used the work in the field of office furniture.

Office furniture as a product category, is seen as quite low-interest. Nearly nobody knows the brand of the furniture he is working with all day.

However it is very remarkable that when there are conflicts in the professional performance of the office worker, he will always focus his complaints on the furniture. The chair at once offers a very bad seating position, the table top is too cold or of the wrong colour, and the drawers of his cabinet are malfunctioning. A whole stack of emotions suddenly appears despite the lack of interest in the product itself.

When you start to design office furniture, first of all you are confronted with all kinds of formal restrictions such as standards and ergonomic specifications. Also you are dependent on purely functional aspects, such as the structure of cable conductors or the desired stiffness of a frame. But, it is quite easy to make from all these aspects a technical basic-layer, from which you can start, to design.

Striking is the fact that even in the field of these technical starting points there is already some fashion recognisable. The structure of desks, with four legs or with a frame of a different shape, is obviously affected by trends. Choosing the wrong structure makes the product old-fashioned even before it seriously has been designed; so even the technical structure of a product can evoke emotions. Something that we don't always teach, or maybe never explain to our students.

When the structure is defined and all the technical constraints are known, the designer will go on with his job by means of an interesting approach. That can be a clever solution for parts of the construction, it

can be new materials, as you will remember from the Loctite story, it can be the inspiration from a new trend in applied arts, such as, for example, post-modernism.

As we started developing this programme, later called ST, we had a mixture of interesting aspects that we would like to integrate in to this new system. The first thing that influenced us was the fact that, as we started the development, it was 1974, the time that was very negative about energy consumption and about the waste of mate-

12 rials. The emotions that were evoked by the negative feelings that were going around had a big influence on the way we would like to design a new office furniture programme. The programme should be very sober, not only in the use of materials but also in design. We intended to use the least material as possible, and with less design as possible.

We thought that, in that way, we could materialise the concern of that period.

A second starting point was the fact that analysts in the field of office work predicted an ongoing increase in working in teams. The individual work would disappear and all the work would be done in small groups, which would be formed, based on the different tasks of the organisation. So we developed a series of tabletops that could be easily linked together and also could easily be changed in configuration. We thought that not only the series should be able to perform in that way, but it also should visualise its flexibility.

We would like to develop huge working areas, without a defined place for the individual.

As a third starting point we wished to develop a structure without borders.

So the tops should be as big as possible, the legs should be as long as possible and be part of a structure from floor to ceiling. These starting points where the basis for sketches and models.

The first emotional threshold was the confrontation of the prototypes with our sales-department. Although they appreciated the functional aspects, such as the possibility to link the table-tops, they were very disappointed by the lack of ornamentation. First reactions, first emotions were very negative and unaccepting.

Striking was the fact that, because the design of this programme was very close to the technical structure, the reactions of this first layer were dominating the reactions of the design itself (the second layer).

That's why the spontaneous emotions, mostly related to the visible structure, overshadowed the advantages of the concept.

Secondly what was very remarkable was the fact that we found out that 'getting used to' has a big influence on the further acceptance and the way the programme could be developed.

However, disk jockeys know all about this phenomena. So, getting used to (an aspect related to time) and the possibility to involve that in the product-user-relation can have a very big impact on the way products evoke emotions.

So also in the further development of our ST programme. After several confrontations with the design, modifications were worked out in the second layer around the programme, the acceptance grew and the programme became the darling of most of the members or our selling staff.

The work on the second layer is also the main design job we teach our students.

We offer them a certain product category, in which they should develop a suitable structure and then start to design the product itself. What we also should teach the students is that even the decisions they make in the first layer are of big importance to the emotions that the product will finally evoke, even when the second layer was thoroughly elaborated.

What we in our programme designed in the second layer had to deal mainly with colour and details: we related the programme very much to the existing brown-beige colour schemes of the mid-seventies.

As we found out later, different customers were attracted to different aspects of our programme. Some of them were mainly attracted by the basic properties of the furniture, such as the possibility to link the tabletops, or the flexibility of the connections, or the possibility to adapt the programme to the style of the company involved. The emotions that one can relate to this acceptance are: inspired, attracted to, fascinated, and pleasantly surprised. Others were mainly attracted by the design itself, the no-nonsense and timeless look, that fit very well in the overall feelings. The emotions that you can relate to this are: appreciation, enthusiasm.

However, it also is interesting to have a look at the third layer, the layer around the product. The first group of customers that appreciated the programme were users of a non-conforming nature. So we started to use this group, their emotions and their behaviour as a leading motivation in our publicity campaign.

"Young, dynamic, warm" were the catchwords. We also noticed that getting familiar to a product played a role in the publicity through the years. As our customers got more familiar with the products we were able to present the products in a less confrontational way, thus enlarging the market in a substantial way.

What did we, as designers, learn from this situation? First of all we learned that already the decisions you make in the first stage of product-design, defining the technical product structure or making decisions in materials, can influence the acceptance of a product in a substantial way. So it is not just the purposeful design in, as I called it, the second layer, that dominates the acceptance of the users emotions.

In the third layer it is of big importance that the designer and his intention play an important role. Otherwise there could arise a situation where the emotions that the first and second layer of the product evoke come in conflict with the emotions that the publicity wants to evoke.

Is a designer aware of the fact that a product causes emotions?

Of course he is. Already in the first confrontation of a model or a prototype with all kinds of decision makers the judgement of a design is mainly based on emotions. But the designer is not aware enough of the role of emotions on this battleground.

There is also a big danger in the way we try to treat these aspects related to design. We only

treat them in a way that knowledge should directly point to commercial success. The customer or user should be enthusiastic about a product, fascinated, inspired and attracted to it. What we found out, as designers, that sometimes it takes a long time to reach that stage, we found out that a designer also must learn to rely on his own position.

Getting used to products plays a much bigger role than we think, and enables the designer to start product design processes not only with a boring acceptance, but also with a thrilling confrontation.

So, it is of absolute importance to give the designer insight in all aspects surrounding product emotion. Insights into the role they play, the way they could or should be used or manipulated need to be given. It is also of importance because the area of design, or the position of the designer becomes more and more threatened by marketeers and trend watchers.

When we discuss product emotion just in the context of marketing, designers will not be very interested. In their opinion marketeers are traditional and conservative, without a vision, without risks. So the emotions that they want to be caused by products are of the same nature. And the same applies for trend watchers. Their self fulfilling prophecies are of more importance to the positioning of a product through publicity than that it could deal with serious product design. It influences a little bit the second layer, but that's all. But because trend watching uses more and more the field of emotions, it is absolutely necessary for a designer to know the relation between product, form and emotions at a scientific level.

So, this conference is of great importance to industrial design and to designers, and of course also to our students and education.